

**YUQORI SINF GEOMETRIYA MAVZUSINI O'QITISHDA YANGI
PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA METODLAR. SINKVEYN
METODI, VENN DIAGRAMMASI METODLARI HAQIDA.**

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar yordamida matematikani o'rganish. Sinkveyn metodi, Venn diagrammasi metodlari haqida.

Kalit so'zlar: Sinkveyn, ko'pyoq, yassi ko'pburchak, Piramida.

Zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalarini loyihalashtirish paytida biz guruh bo'lib ishlashni tanlaymiz. Lekin bunda, ta'lim berish usullariga bog'liq holda, uni qo'yilgan ta'lim maqsadlariga, rejalashtirilgan natijalarga va boshqalarga mos kelishi hisobga olinadi.

Sinkveyn metodi.

Sinkveyn fransuzcha so'z bo'lib "besh" degan ma'noni bildiradi. o'quvchilarga darsni mustahkamlash bosqichida biror geometrik shakl, matematik atama, hodisa nomi, matematik olimni quyidagicha besh qatorli misraga solishni taklif etish lozim.

Ot (1 so'z)

Sifat (2 so'z)

Fe'l (3 so'z)

Ibora (gap bilan ta'rifi beriladi)

Sinonim (1 so'z yoziladi, otga yozilgan so'z bilan ma'nosi bir xil bo'lsin).

Masalan mavzu: "Piramida "

1. Ko'pyoq

2. Qavariq, 8 qirrali

3. Yasash, yo'naltirish, hisoblash.

4. Piramida yassi ko'pburchak - piramida asosidan, asos tekisligida yotmagan nuqta - piramida uchidan va uchni asosining nuqtalari bilan tutashtiruvchi hamma kesmalardan iborat. (chegaralangan)

5. Geometrik shakl

Sinkveyn metodidan foydalanish o'quvchilarni chuqur mulohaza qilishga o'rgatadi.

Venn diagrammasi.

«Venn diagrammasi» qiyosiy taxlilda juda qoʻl kelib, mavzuni sharxlab, ikki muammoni bir-biriga muqoyasa qilib oʻtishda qulay usuldir. Bu usul ikki doira shaklidagi aylana chiziqlarning qoʻshilishi holatida boʻlib doiralarning ikki tarafiga tanlangan mavzuning faqat oʻziga xos individual xususiyatlari yozilib, oʻrtada ikki doiraning qoʻshilishi natijasida paydo boʻlgan boʻshliqda esa tanlangan ikki mavzuga xos turli fikrlar, xususiyatlar gʻoyalar koʻrinishi izohlab boriladi. Bir qarashda oddiydek tuyulgan bu usul oʻquvchilarning fikrlash qobiliyatini oshiradi, xotirani kuchaytiradi. U yoki bu mavzu ustida mustaqil ishlashga undaydi. Ikki mavzuning umumiy va individual, yaʼni faqat oʻziga xos tomonlarini tez farqlaydi. Mavzu tez va uzoq vaqt esda qoladi. «Venn diagrammasi» oʻquvchini hushyorlikka, sezgirlikka chorlaydi. Oʻquvchilar 4—5 tadan uch guruhga, jami 15 taga ajratiladi. 1-guruh doiraning oʻng tomoni, 2-guruh doiraning chap tomoni, 3-guruh ikki doiraning qoʻshilishidan paydo boʻlgan boʻshliq ustida ishlaydi. Mavzuni keng qamrovli oʻzlashtirib olishga koʻmaklashadi. Guruxdagi qolgan oʻquvchilar esa kuzatuvchilardir, yaʼni «Venn diagrammasi» ustida ishlayotgan 3 guruhning harakatlarini kuzatadilar. Hatto baholashlari ham mumkin. Dars, mavzu, harakatlar uzoq vaqt esda saqlanib qoladi. «Venn diagrammasi» turli xil gʻoya, fikrlar kurashi va hujumini, munozaralarni keltirib chi-qaradi. Oʻquvchilarni oʻylantiradi, mustaqil fikrlashga undaydi.

Bu metod oʻquvchini kattaliklarni qiyoslashga undaydi. quyidagiday doiralar chiziladi. Ikkita kattalik taqqoslanadi. Bir xil jihatlari oʻrtada (aylanalar kesishgan qismida) yoziladi. Oʻziga xos jihatlari aylanada yoziladi

Venn diagrammasi

1-da piramidaning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari yoziladi.

3- da kesik piramidaning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari yoziladi.

2-da har ikkala piramidaga xos xos xususiyatlari yoziladi.

Bundan ham algebra, ham geometriya darslarida qo`llash mumkin.

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